

Formatted map examples

Region map

Your Waterfowl Hunting Areas

The following map shows several waterfowl hunting areas in Northern California.

1. In the past 2 years, did you hunt waterfowl in any of these areas?

	Yes	No
1. Upper Butte Basin Wildlife Area	☐	☐
2. Gray Lodge Wildlife Area	☐	☐
3. Fremont Weir Wildlife Area	☐	☐
4. Yolo Basin Wildlife Area	☐	☐
5. Grizzly Island Wildlife Area	☐	☐
6. North Bay	☐	☐
7. South Bay	☐	☐

Drill-down site map for restoration areas

South Bay Waterfowl Areas

Below is a map of waterfowl hunting areas within the South Bay area that indicates areas shaded in **green**.

2. In the past 2 years, when you hunted waterfowl in the South Bay region, did you go to any of the **green** areas of the map?

Yes

No